

Effects adhesive thickness on the interface performance of FRP-concrete structure

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Abstract: The interface performance of FRP-concrete is the basis of mechanical analysis for FRP (Fiber Reinforced Polymer) reinforced concrete structure. Many researchers had studied the problem and proposed many different kinds of interface constitutive models. In the study, the comparative analysis on several interface constitutive models commonly adopted in engineering were carried out. It is found that the thickness of adhesive has important influences on performance of FRP-concrete. The finite element program ABAQUS was used to simulate the interface behavior of FRP-concrete by changing the adhesive thickness (1mm, 2mm, 3mm, 4mm). Effects of adhesive thickness on the ultimate loading bearing capacity, interface constitutive model with three important parameters and the effective bond length of FRP-concrete interface. Some conclusions were drawn as follows:

- (1) Adhesive thickness has evident influence on the ultimate loading bearing capacity of FRP-concrete interface. The loading bearing capacity goes up with the increase of the adhesive thickness from 1mm to 2mm and reaches the ultimate value when the adhesive thickness is 2 mm. while the loading bearing capacity gets down with decrease of the adhesive thickness from 2mm to 4mm.
- (2) The interface shear stiffness and the ultimate shear stress decrease with increasing of adhesive thickness, while the interfacial fracture energy increases at the same time.
- (3) According to stress contour plots of bonding interfaces with different adhesive thickness at the ultimate loads state, it is found that the effective bond length increases with increasing of adhesive thickness obviously.

Keywords:FRP-concrete; Interface property; Constitutive model; Numerical simulation; Adhesive thickness

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